

CitySCAPE

Risk analysis and impact assessment engine

Financial impact assessment engine

Collaborative threat investigation platform

IDS/IPS engines

SIEM as a Correlation engine with backlog of markers

Collaborative security incident response platform

Training

The CitySCAPE Solution

CitySCAPE introduces innovative risk analysis techniques and orchestrates a number of software solutions to realize an interoperable toolkit that seamlessly integrates to any multimodal transport system.

More specifically, the CitySCAPE software toolkit will:

- Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats

- Evaluate an attack's impact in both technical and financial terms
- Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero-day attacks
- Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT/CSIRT authorities and support their interplay.

CitySCAPE At a Glance

Consortium

Project Facts

- **Duration:** 36 months (September 2020-August 2023)
- **EU funding:** 4 998 057.88 €
- **Pilots:** Tallinn, Estonia / Genova, Italy
- **Project Coordinator:** Dr Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) a.amditis@iccs.gr

